

Metadata for Fieldwork Ethnographic Material

Title: Sense of Belonging, Community and Engagement in Exiled Queerhood

Description: The data was collected for the doctoral thesis *Queer in Exile and Exile in Queer* (Ali 2023c) between 2020-2022 from fieldwork participant observation at a queer support group hosted by Helsinki Pride Yhteisö. The data were collected from meetings, recreational activities and public events of the group every second week. Each meeting lasted for about 3 hours, and notes were taken of participants' activities and statements during the meetings. This was followed up by reflection and elaboration on these after the meetings. The focus was on narratives of belonging and community among participants: how these play out in everyday relations at the community center and the support group in lay encounters and low-key conversations and how participants narrate and mobilize this in their mundane life in Finland and in encounters with state officials.

Date of Data Collection: June 2020 – June 2022

Keywords: Queer Exile, LGBTQ organizations, Refugees, Asylum Seekers, Migration

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Publications on the Material:

Ali, A. 2024. Chronic Pain of Race and Citizenship, Profound Subtleties of Injury and Redress in a Community of Queer Exiles. *Nordic Journal of Migration Research*, 14(2): (1–16). DOI: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33134/njmr.723>

Ali, A. 2024 Queer Crisis: Turbulent Journeys in Gender and Nation, *SQS – Journal of Queer Studies in Finland*. 18(3), 69–74. <https://doi.org/10.23980/sqs.154809>.

Ali, A. 2023a. Warming up narratives of community: Queer kinship and emotional exile. *Intersections. East European Journal of Society and Politics*. (8)4: (10–24). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17356/ieejsp.v8i4.1014>.

Ali, A. 2023b. On purpose: solidarity by accident or design and the generative ambiguity in between. *Space and Polity*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562576.2023.2292255>

Ali A. 2023c, *Queer in Exile and Exile in Queer*, Ph.D thesis Helsinki, University of Helsinki. Available at: <<http://hdl.handle.net/10138/565658>> (Accessed: 6. May 2025)

Ali, A. 2022, Reframing the Subject, in Eds. Kmak, M & Björklund, H. *Refugees and Knowledge Production: Europe's Past and Present*, Routledge (pp. 182-198) DOI: 10.4324/9781003092421-14

Preservation of the data: The data is preserved meanwhile three texts are being written as a spin spinoff of the doctoral studies. Previously the data were stored on University of Helsinki servers. Now the data are anonymized on a personal computer meanwhile texts are finalized. As per agreement with the participants and the gatekeepers (and as stated during the ethical review procedures statement number: 55/2020), the data will be deleted and will not be available for the public.